

FAME TRAINING CATALOGUE

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Introduction

The FAME Training Catalogue has been developed to support the [FAME](#) project's mission of advancing knowledge, skills, and capacity building across Artificial Intelligence, Data Spaces, Federated Learning, and other emerging technologies relevant to the financial and manufacturing sectors. Rather than creating new training materials from scratch, FAME adopts a strategic approach that **leverages, integrates, and curates high-quality third-party learning resources** already available in the wider educational ecosystem.

This catalogue brings together a diverse selection of courses, training programmes, and learning modules offered by established academic institutions and global education platforms such as **Coursera, edX, Udemy**, and others. Its purpose is to provide a **structured, centralised overview** of external learning opportunities that can benefit stakeholders across the FAME ecosystem, including researchers, practitioners, industry professionals, students, and policymakers.

The foundation of the catalogue builds upon the work conducted in the **INFINITECH** project, where an initial collection of training resources was created. FAME extends this effort significantly: the current catalogue includes **over 170 curated courses**, of which **more than 50 entries originate from INFINITECH**, enriched with additional metadata, updated links, and new resources aligned with the technological focus of the project.

Each entry in the catalogue is described using a standardised metadata structure to facilitate transparency, comparability, and ease of discovery. The metadata model includes:

- **Course Provider:** The organisation or platform delivering the course.
- **Type:** Delivery format (e.g., face-to-face, online, self-paced, synchronous/asynchronous).
- **Level:** Target difficulty (e.g., beginner, intermediate, advanced).
- **Duration:** Estimated course workload in hours.
- **Cost:** Participation fee, where applicable.
- **Location:** Physical location for on-site training.
- **Keywords:** Searchable descriptors and thematic tags.
- **URL:** Direct link to the original course webpage.

By curating and consolidating this wide range of external resources, the FAME Training Catalogue provides an **expandable repository** that supports continuous learning and skill development. It enables users to identify relevant training opportunities efficiently and contributes to the broader objective of fostering an informed, capable, and innovation-driven community within the FAME project and beyond.

Course	Keywords	Platform	Provider	Level	Duration	Cost	Location
<u>IDS Tech Talk Evolving data space concepts – upcoming updates to the IDS RAM & Rulebook</u>	data spaces, trusted data sharing, interoperability	YouTube	International Data Spaces Association (IDSA)	All levels	1h	Free	Virtual
<u>Digital Transformation in Financial Services Specialization</u>	digital transformation, financial services	Course	CBS	Beginner	3h/week x 5 months	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Innovation Strategy: Developing Your Fintech strategy</u>	innovation, fintech	Course	CBS	Beginner	11h	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Future Development in Supply Chain Finance and Blockchain Technology</u>	blockchain, supply chain, finance	Course	New York Institute of Finance	Intermediate	7h	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Machine Learning and Reinforcement Learning in Finance Specialization</u>	machine learning, finance	Course	NYU	Intermediate	5h/week x 4 months	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>FinTech: Finance Industry Transformation and</u>	finance, digital transformation	Course	The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology	Beginner	3h/week x 5 months	Course Plus	Virtual

<u>Regulation Specialization</u>							
<u>Guided Tour of Machine Learning in Finance</u>	machine learning, finance	Course	NYU	Intermediate	24h	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Using Machine Learning in Trading and Finance</u>	machine learning, trading	Course	New York Institute of Finance	Intermediate	19h	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Reinforcement Learning in Finance</u>	reinforcement learning, finance	Course	NYU	Advanced	17h	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Fundamentals of Machine Learning in Finance</u>	machine learning, finance	Course	NYU	Intermediate	18h	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Overview of Advanced Methods of Reinforcement Learning in Finance</u>	reinforcement learning, finance	Course	NYU	Advanced	13h	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Supply Chain Finance and Blockchain Technology Specialization</u>	blockchain, supply chain, finance	Course	New York Institute of Finance	Intermediate	3h/week x 4 months	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Blockchain, Cryptocurrencies, and Decentralized Finance</u>	blockchain, decentralized finance	Course	INSEAD	Beginner	19h	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Introduction to Blockchain for</u>	blockchain, supply chain, finance	Course	INSEAD	Beginner	29h	Course Plus	Virtual

<u>Financial Services</u>							
<u>Blockchain Transformations of Financial Services</u>	blockchain, supply chain, finance	Course	INSEAD	Beginner	16h	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Blockchain Revolution Specialization</u>	blockchain, supply chain, finance	Course	INSEAD	Beginner	4h/week x 5 months	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Digital transformation-Finance-Strategies</u>	digital transformation, financial services	Udemy	-	All levels	1h	€12	Virtual
<u>Open Banking, PSD2 and GDPR, FinTech</u>	fintech, open banking	Udemy	-	All levels	2.5h	€12	Virtual
<u>Finance and Accounting in the Digital Age</u>	finance, digital transformation	Udemy	-	All levels	1.5h	€12	Virtual
<u>Artificial Intelligence for Finance, Accounting & Auditing</u>	finance, digital transformation	Udemy	AI Ascent LLC	All levels	5.5h	€12	Virtual
<u>Complete 2-in-1 Python for Business and Finance Bootcamp</u>	data science, statistics, python	Udemy	-	All levels	37.5h	€16.99	Virtual
<u>Practical Machine Learning: Real World Projects In Finance</u>	data science, machine learning, finance	Udemy	TheMachineLearning.Org	Beginner	3.5h	€12	Virtual
<u>AI for Finance</u>	ai, finance	Udemy	Packt Publishing	Intermediate	2.5h	€12	Virtual

<u>Mastering FinTech and Machine Learning!</u>	machine learning, fintech	Ude my	Mammoth Interactive	All levels	110h	€12	Virtu al
<u>Machine Learning Practical: Real World Projects In Finance</u>	machine learning, finance	Ude my	TheMachineLearning.Org	All levels	3.5h	€12	Virtu al
<u>FinTech - Prepare for the revolution in Finance</u>	innovation, AI, blockchain, machine learning	Ude my	-	Beginner	3.5h	€12	Virtu al
<u>Blockchain For Business+Finance Professionals 2019</u>	blockchain, business, finance, banking	Ude my	Up Degree	Beginner	7.5h	€12	Virtu al
<u>Blockchain In Banking Industry & Enterprise Application</u>	fintech, blockchain, business, finance	Ude my	-	Intermediate	2.5h	€12	Virtu al
<u>AI and Blockchain : A Disruptive Integration</u>	AI, blockchain	Ude my	-	Intermediate	4h	€12	Virtu al
<u>Introduction to FinTech</u>	finance, digital transformation	edX	University of Hong Kong	Beginner	1-3h x 6 weeks	€165	Virtu al
<u>Fintech: Blockchain for Business and Finance</u>	fintech, blockchain, business, finance	edX	University of Texas at Austin	Beginner	5-6h x 4 weeks	€704	Virtu al
<u>Fintech: AI & Machine Learning in the</u>	AI, fintech	edX	University of Texas at Austin	Beginner	5-6h x 4 weeks	€704	Virtu al

<u>Financial Industry</u>							
<u>Deep Learning and Neural Networks for Financial Engineering</u>	deep learning, networks, financial engineering	edX	NYU	Intermediate	4-6 h x 7 weeks	€662	Virtual
<u>FinTech Ethics and Risks</u>	fintech, ethics	edX	University of Hong Kong	Beginner	1-5h x 6 weeks	€165	Virtual
<u>Classical Machine Learning for Financial Engineering</u>	machine learning, finance	edX	NYU	Intermediate	4-6 h x 7 weeks	€662	Virtual
<u>Fintech: Overview of the Fintech Sector</u>	machine learning, finance	edX	University of Texas at Austin	Intermediate	5-6h x 3 weeks	€497	Virtual
<u>Blockchain and FinTech: Basics, Applications, and Limitations</u>	blockchain, supply chain, finance	edX	University of Hong Kong	Beginner	3-4h x 6 weeks	€165	Virtual
<u>Introduction to Hyperledger Blockchain Technologies</u>	blockchain, distributed ledgers	edX	The Linux Foundation	Beginner	2-4h x 10 weeks	€165	Virtual
<u>Blockchain: Understanding Its Uses and Implications</u>	blockchain, implications	edX	The Linux Foundation	Beginner	2-3h x 14 weeks	€123	Virtual

<u>MSc in Digital Currency</u>	blockchain, digital currencies		University of Nicosia	Beginner	3 semesters / 1 year	€12,960	Distance Learning
<u>MSc in Computer Science, Concentration in Blockchain Technologies</u>	blockchain		University of Nicosia	Beginner	3 semesters / 1 year	TBD	Distance Learning
<u>Blockchain Technologies: Business Innovation and Application</u>	blockchain, decentralized finance		MIT	Beginner	5-8 hours x 6 weeks	TBD	Distance Learning
<u>Fintech: Embedded Finance, Payments, BaaS and API Banking</u>	embedded finance, payments, BaaS, API banking	Udemy	Global FinTech Academy	Intermediate	2.5 hours	€20	Virtual
<u>NYIF: Option Pricing and Applications</u>	embedded finance	edX	NYIF	Intermediate	1-2 hours/week	€253	Virtual
<u>IMD: Blockchain and the Future of Finance</u>	open banking	edX	IMD Real Learning	All levels	5 weeks, 1-2 hours/week	TBD	Virtual
<u>Digital Banking - Masterclass & Introduction to Fintech</u>	open banking	Udemy	-	Intermediate	9.5 hours	€70	Virtual
<u>Embedded Systems Essentials with Arm</u>	embedded systems, Arm technology	edX	Arm Education	Intermediate	6 weeks, 2-3 hours/week	Free, cert €92	Virtual

<u>Artificial Intelligence for Everyone</u>	artificial intelligence, AI	Coursera	Deeplearning.ai	Beginner	6 hours	Free, optional cert	Virtual
<u>Data Science and Machine Learning Bootcamp</u>	data trading, machine learning	Udemy	Pierian Training	All Levels	17.5 hours	€70	Virtual
<u>Digital Marketing Specialization</u>	monetization, digital marketing	Coursera	University of Illinois	Beginner	4 months, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Blockchain Basics</u>	self-sovereign identities, blockchain	Coursera	University at Buffalo	Beginner	15 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>FPGA Design for Embedded Systems Specialization</u>	FPGA, CPLD, embedded systems	Coursera	University of Colorado Boulder	Intermediate	2 months, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Real-Time Embedded Systems Specialization</u>	real-time systems, debugging	Coursera	University of Colorado Boulder	Intermediate	5 months, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Development of Secure Embedded Systems Specialization</u>	secure embedded systems, RTOS	Coursera	EIT Digital	Intermediate	2 months, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Fintech: Buy Now Pay Later (BNPL)</u>	buy now pay later, BNPL	Udemy	Global FinTech Academy	All Levels	2.5 hours	€20	Virtual
<u>Financial Management Specialization</u>	financial management, fintech	Coursera	University of Illinois	Intermediate	3 months, 10 hours/week	\$79/month	Virtual
<u>Data Management</u>	data management	Coursera	Vanderbilt University	Intermediate	3 weeks,	Course Plus	Virtual

<u>nt for Clinical Research</u>	ent, clinical research				5 hours/week		
<u>Big Data Specialization</u>	big data, data spaces	Course	UC San Diego	Intermediate	3 months, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Applied AI with DeepLearning</u>	applied AI, deep learning	Course	IBM	Intermediate	25 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Introduction to Trading, Machine Learning & GCP</u>	data trading, machine learning, GCP	Course	Google Cloud	Intermediate	9 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>The Strategy of Content Marketing</u>	content marketing, monetization	Course	UC Davis	Intermediate	3 weeks, 6 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Blockchain Specialization</u>	blockchain, self-sovereign identity	Course	University at Buffalo	Intermediate	2 months, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Data Engineering on Google Cloud Platform</u>	data engineering, Google Cloud	Course	Google Cloud	Intermediate	1 month, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Introduction to Artificial Intelligence (AI)</u>	AI, machine learning	Course	IBM	Beginner	3 weeks, 2 hours/week	\$49	Virtual
<u>IBM AI Engineering Professional Certificate</u>	AI engineering, neural networks	Course	IBM	Intermediate	1 month, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Deep Learning Specialization</u>	deep learning, neural networks,	Course	DeepLearning.AI	Intermediate	3 months, 10 hours/week	\$49/month	Virtual

	TensorFlow						
<u>AI Foundations for Everyone Specialization</u>	AI fundamentals, machine learning	Course	IBM	Beginner	1 month, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>AI for Scientific Research Specialization</u>	AI research, machine learning	Course	LearnQuest	Intermediate	1 month, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Data Management and Visualization</u>	data management, visualization	Course	Wesleyan University	Beginner	12 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Data Engineering, Big Data, and ML on GCP</u>	data engineering, big data, GCP	Course	Google Cloud	Intermediate	1 month, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Future of Fintech: Open Banking, GDPR and PSD2</u>	fintech, open banking, GDPR, PSD2	Udemy	-	Intermediate	2.5 hours	€20	Virtual
<u>Automotive Embedded Systems & Applications</u>	automotive, embedded systems	Udemy	-	Intermediate	30 hours	€40	Virtual
<u>Artificial Intelligence A-Z: Build 7 AI Models</u>	AI, deep learning, neural networks	Udemy	-	All Levels	16 hours	€90	Virtual
<u>10 Days of No Code AI Bootcamp</u>	no code AI, machine learning	Udemy	-	All Levels	12.5 hours	€70	Virtual
<u>AI Mastery: Python's Odyssey in AI</u>	AI mastery, Python	Udemy	-	All Levels	7 hours	€50	Virtual

<u>Blockchain In Banking Industry & Enterprise Application</u>	fintech, blockchain, business, finance	Udemy	-	Intermediate	2.5h	€12	Virtual
<u>AI and Blockchain: A Disruptive Integration</u>	AI, blockchain	Udemy	-	Intermediate	4h	€12	Virtual
<u>Introduction to FinTech</u>	finance, digital transformation	edX	University of Hong Kong	Beginner	1-3h x 6 weeks	€165	Virtual
<u>Fintech: Blockchain for Business and Finance</u>	fintech, blockchain, business, finance	edX	University of Texas at Austin	Beginner	5-6h x 4 weeks	€704	Virtual
<u>Fintech: AI & Machine Learning in the Financial Industry</u>	AI, fintech	edX	University of Texas at Austin	Beginner	5-6h x 4 weeks	€704	Virtual
<u>Deep Learning and Neural Networks for Financial Engineering</u>	deep learning, networks, financial engineering	edX	NYU	Intermediate	4-6 h x 7 weeks	€662	Virtual
<u>FinTech Ethics and Risks</u>	fintech, ethics	edX	University of Hong Kong	Beginner	1-5h x 6 weeks	€165	Virtual
<u>Classical Machine Learning for Financial Engineering</u>	machine learning, finance	edX	NYU	Intermediate	4-6 h x 7 weeks	€662	Virtual
<u>Fintech: Overview of the</u>	machine learning, finance	edX	University of Texas at Austin	Intermediate	5-6h x 3 weeks	€497	Virtual

<u>Fintech Sector</u>							
<u>Blockchain and FinTech: Basics, Applications, and Limitations</u>	blockchain, supply chain, finance	edX	University of Hong Kong	Beginner	3-4h x 6 weeks	€165	Virtual
<u>Introduction to Hyperledger Blockchain Technologies</u>	blockchain, distributed ledgers	edX	The Linux Foundation	Beginner	2-4h x 10 weeks	€165	Virtual
<u>Blockchain: Understanding Its Uses and Implications</u>	blockchain, implications	edX	The Linux Foundation	Beginner	2-3h x 14 weeks	€123	Virtual
<u>MSc in Digital Currency</u>	blockchain, digital currencies		University of Nicosia	Beginner	3 semesters / 1 year	€12,960	Distance Learning
<u>MSc in Computer Science, Concentration in Blockchain Technologies</u>	blockchain		University of Nicosia	Beginner	3 semesters / 1 year	TBD	Distance Learning
<u>Blockchain Technologies: Business Innovation and Application</u>	blockchain, decentralized finance		MIT	Beginner	5-8 hours x 6 weeks	TBD	Distance Learning
<u>Fintech: Embedded Finance, Payments, BaaS and</u>	embedded finance, payments, BaaS, API banking	Udemy	Global FinTech Academy	Intermediate	2.5 hours	€20	Virtual

<u>API Banking</u>							
<u>NYIF: Option Pricing and Applications</u>	embedded finance	edX	NYIF	Intermediate	1-2 hours/week	€253	Virtual
<u>IMD: Blockchain and the Future of Finance</u>	open banking	edX	IMD Real Learning	All levels	5 weeks, 1-2 hours/week	TBD	Virtual
<u>Digital Banking - Masterclass & Introduction to Fintech</u>	open banking	Udemy	-	Intermediate	9.5 hours	€70	Virtual
<u>Embedded Systems Essentials with Arm</u>	embedded systems, Arm technology	edX	Arm Education	Intermediate	6 weeks, 2-3 hours/week	Free, cert €92	Virtual
<u>Artificial Intelligence for Everyone</u>	artificial intelligence, AI	Coursera	Deeplearning.ai	Beginner	6 hours	Free, optional cert	Virtual
<u>Data Science and Machine Learning Bootcamp</u>	data trading, machine learning	Udemy	Pierian Training	All Levels	17.5 hours	€70	Virtual
<u>Digital Marketing Specialization</u>	monetization, digital marketing	Coursera	University of Illinois	Beginner	4 months, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Blockchain Basics</u>	self-sovereign identities, blockchain	Coursera	University at Buffalo	Beginner	15 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>FPGA Design for Embedded Systems</u>	FPGA, CPLD, embedded systems	Coursera	University of Colorado Boulder	Intermediate	2 months, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual

<u>Specialization</u>							
<u>Real-Time Embedded Systems Specialization</u>	real-time systems, debugging	Coursera	University of Colorado Boulder	Intermediate	5 months, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Development of Secure Embedded Systems Specialization</u>	secure embedded systems, RTOS	Coursera	EIT Digital	Intermediate	2 months, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Fintech: Buy Now Pay Later (BNPL)</u>	buy now pay later, BNPL	Udemy	Global FinTech Academy	All Levels	2.5 hours	€20	Virtual
<u>Financial Management Specialization</u>	financial management, fintech	Coursera	University of Illinois	Intermediate	3 months, 10 hours/week	\$79/month	Virtual
<u>Data Management for Clinical Research</u>	data management, clinical research	Coursera	Vanderbilt University	Intermediate	3 weeks, 5 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Big Data Specialization</u>	big data, data spaces	Coursera	UC San Diego	Intermediate	3 months, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Applied AI with DeepLearning</u>	applied AI, deep learning	Coursera	IBM	Intermediate	25 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Introduction to Trading, Machine Learning & GCP</u>	data trading, machine learning, GCP	Coursera	Google Cloud	Intermediate	9 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>The Strategy of Content Marketing</u>	content marketing, monetization	Coursera	UC Davis	Intermediate	3 weeks, 6 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual

<u>Blockchain Specialization</u>	blockchain, self-sovereign identity	Course	University at Buffalo	Intermediate	2 months, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Data Engineering on Google Cloud Platform</u>	data engineering, Google Cloud	Course	Google Cloud	Intermediate	1 month, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Introduction to Artificial Intelligence (AI)</u>	AI, machine learning	Course	IBM	Beginner	3 weeks, 2 hours/week	\$49	Virtual
<u>IBM AI Engineering Professional Certificate</u>	AI engineering, neural networks	Course	IBM	Intermediate	1 month, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Deep Learning Specialization</u>	deep learning, neural networks, TensorFlow	Course	DeepLearning.AI	Intermediate	3 months, 10 hours/week	\$49/month	Virtual
<u>AI Foundations for Everyone Specialization</u>	AI fundamentals, machine learning	Course	IBM	Beginner	1 month, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>AI for Scientific Research Specialization</u>	AI research, machine learning	Course	LearnQuest	Intermediate	1 month, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Data Management and Visualization</u>	data management, visualization	Course	Wesleyan University	Beginner	12 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Data Engineering, Big Data, and ML on GCP</u>	data engineering, big data, GCP	Course	Google Cloud	Intermediate	1 month, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual

<u>Future of Fintech: Open Banking, GDPR and PSD2</u>	fintech, open banking, GDPR, PSD2	Udemy	-	Intermediate	2.5 hours	€20	Virtual
<u>Automotive Embedded Systems & Applications</u>	automotive, embedded systems	Udemy	-	Intermediate	30 hours	€40	Virtual
<u>Artificial Intelligence A-Z: Build 7 AI Models</u>	AI, deep learning, neural networks	Udemy	-	All Levels	16 hours	€90	Virtual
<u>10 Days of No Code AI Bootcamp</u>	no code AI, machine learning	Udemy	-	All Levels	12.5 hours	€70	Virtual
<u>AI Mastery: Python's Odyssey in AI</u>	AI mastery, Python	Udemy	-	All Levels	7 hours	€50	Virtual
<u>The Complete AI for Professionals</u>	AI for professionals	Udemy	-	All Levels	8 hours	€50	Virtual
<u>PyTorch: Deep Learning and AI</u>	PyTorch, deep learning	Udemy	-	All Levels	2.5 hours	€85	Virtual
<u>Advanced AI: Deep Reinforcement Learning</u>	advanced AI, reinforcement learning	Udemy	-	All Levels	10.5 hours	€25	Virtual
<u>AI & Machine Learning from Scratch</u>	AI, machine learning	Udemy	-	All Levels	6.5 hours	€50	Virtual
<u>AI and Machine Learning</u>	AI fundamentals,	Udemy	-	All Levels	8 hours	€20	Virtual

<u>Fundamentals</u>	machine learning						
<u>Modern AI with Zero Coding</u>	AI, no coding	Udemy	-	All Levels	9.5 hours	€60	Virtual
<u>Tableau 2024 A-Z Training</u>	data training, analytics	Udemy	-	Intermediate	8.5 hours	€70	Virtual
<u>Data Security and Privacy Training</u>	data training	Udemy	-	Intermediate	1 hour	€20	Virtual
<u>Introduction to Finance: The Role of Financial Markets</u>	data training	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	6 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Data Monetization, Management, and Trends</u>	monetization	edX	IE University	Intermediate	2-4 hours	Free	Virtual
<u>Complete Digital Marketing Guide - 25 Courses</u>	monetization, digital marketing	Udemy	-	All Levels	77.5 hours	€15	Virtual
<u>IBM Project Manager Professional Certificate</u>	data spaces	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) Specialization</u>	data spaces	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	10 hours/week	Free	Virtual
<u>Data Analyst Course: Complete Bootcamp</u>	data collection, preprocessing,	Udemy	-	Intermediate	20.5 hours	€18	Virtual

	visualization						
Data Center Essentials	data spaces	Udemy	-	Intermediate	2.5 hours	€15	Virtual
Leading the Modern Day Business Specialization	data trading	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	1 month, 10 hours/week	Free	Virtual
IBM Data Science Professional Certificate	data trading	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	5 months, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
Infonomics I: Business Information Economics	monetization, economics	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	13 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
Generative AI Essentials	monetization, impact	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	3 weeks, 1 hour/week	Course Plus	Virtual
GPT Vision: Seeing World through Generative AI	data spaces	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	3 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
Introduction to Trading with Technical Analysis	data trading	edX	NYIF		3 months, 2-3 hours/week	€413	Virtual
Python for Data Science and Machine Learning	data science, machine learning	edX	Harvard University		4 months, 3-4 hours/week	€496	Virtual
Data Monetization Strategy	monetization, economics	edX	MIT Sloan		6 weeks, 6-8	TBD	Virtual

					hours/ week		
<u>Investment Banking and Finance: Private Equity</u>	fundraising, valuation	Ude my	-	Interme diate	9 hours	€15	Virtu al
<u>Intro to Traffic Flow Modeling</u>	managem ent schemes	edX	EPFL	Interme diate	7 weeks, 5-6 hours/ week	Free	Virtu al
<u>New Space Economy</u>	federated data managem ent	edX	EPFL	Interme diate	7 weeks, 2-3 hours/ week	Free	Virtu al
<u>Data Analysis for Managem ent</u>	federated data managem ent	edX	LSE	Interme diate	8 weeks, 7-10 hours/ week	Free	Virtu al
<u>Data Analysis</u>	business strategy	edX	University of Cape Town	Interme diate	8 weeks, 7-11 hours/ week	Free	Virtu al
<u>Data Science in Real Estate</u>	federated data managem ent	edX	MIT	Interme diate	6 weeks, 7-10 hours/ week	Free	Virtu al
<u>Data Storytelling with Power BI</u>	federated data managem ent	Cours era	Coursera	Interme diate	12 hours, 3 weeks	Course ra Plus	Virtu al
<u>TensorFlow : Data and Deploymen t Specializati on</u>	federated data managem ent	Cours era	Coursera	Interme diate	1 month, 10 hours/ week	Free	Virtu al
<u>Clinical Data Science Specializati on</u>	federated data managem ent	Cours era	Coursera	Interme diate	2 months , 10 hours/ week	Course ra Plus	Virtu al

<u>Human Factors in AI</u>	federated data management	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	17 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>SIEM Splunk Hands-On Guide Specialization</u>	data analysis	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	3 months, 3 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Brand Management: Strategies for Strong Brand</u>	strategies, data management	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	3 weeks, 1 hour/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Introduction to Big Data</u>	federated data management	Coursera	UC San Diego	Intermediate	17 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Risk Management: Use of Access Controls</u>	control, risk, management	Coursera	ISC2	Intermediate	6 hours	Free	Virtual
<u>HI-FIVE: Health Informatics</u>	innovation, management, value	Coursera	Columbia University	Intermediate	3 weeks, 13 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Introduction to Clinical Data Science</u>	clinical data	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	8 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Customer Analytics</u>	analytics, business	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	11 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Data Science for Business Innovation</u>	business, innovation, management	Coursera	EIT Digital	Intermediate	3 weeks, 2 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Turn Ethical Frameworks into Actions</u>	frameworks, data management	Coursera	CertNexus	Intermediate	15 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Key Success</u>	chain finance	Coursera	NYIF	Intermediate	18 hours	Course Plus	Virtual

<u>Factors in Supply Chain Finance</u>							
<u>Smart Cities – Smart Urban Infrastructures</u>	federated data management	Coursera	EPFL	Intermediate	3 weeks, 4 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Data Management Masterclass</u>	federated data management	Udemy	-	Intermediate	10 hours	€65	Virtual
<u>Master Data Management (MDM)</u>	federated data management	Udemy	-	Intermediate	4 hours	€65	Virtual
<u>Fundamentals of Data Product Management</u>	data product management	Udemy	-	Intermediate	7.5 hours	€60	Virtual
<u>Data Quality Masterclass</u>	data quality management	Udemy	-	Intermediate	6 hours	€70	Virtual
<u>IBM: AI for Everyone: Master the Basics</u>	artificial intelligence	edX	IBM	Intermediate	4 weeks, 1-2 hours/week	Free	Virtual
<u>CS50's Introduction to AI with Python</u>	artificial intelligence	edX	Harvard	Intermediate	7 weeks, 10-30 hours/week	Free	Virtual
<u>AI For Everyone</u>	AI	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	3 weeks, 2 hours/week	Free	Virtual
<u>Artificial Intelligence A-Z 2024</u>	artificial intelligence	Udemy	-	Intermediate	15.5 hours	€90	Virtual
<u>Complete AI and</u>	artificial intelligence	Udemy	-	Intermediate	12 hours	€70	Virtual

<u>ChatGPT Course</u>							
<u>Complete A.I. & ML, Data Science Bootcamp</u>	artificial intelligence	Udemy	-	Intermediate	43.5 hours	€85	Virtual
<u>IBM AI Developer Professional Certificate</u>	AI developer	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	6 months, 4 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>AI For Business Specialization</u>	artificial intelligence	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	1 month, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Machine Learning Specialization</u>	artificial intelligence	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	2 months, 10 hours/week	Free	Virtual
<u>Generative AI for Everyone</u>	artificial intelligence	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	3 weeks, 1 hour/week	Free	Virtual
<u>AI: Ethics & Societal Challenges</u>	societal challenges	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	3 weeks, 4 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>IBM AI Product Manager Professional Certificate</u>	artificial intelligence	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	6 months, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Generative AI with Large Language Models</u>	artificial intelligence	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	3 weeks, 5 hours/week	Free	Virtual
<u>Artificial Intelligence in Marketing</u>	intelligence, marketing	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	3 weeks, 3 hours/week	Free	Virtual

<u>Google Business Intelligence Professional Certificate</u>	intelligence, marketing	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	2 months, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Machine Learning for All</u>	intelligence, marketing	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	3 weeks, 7 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Certified AI Practitioner Certificate</u>	intelligence, marketing	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	2 months, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Introduction to Machine Learning</u>	intelligence, marketing	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	3 weeks, 8 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Intel® AI Fundamentals Specialization</u>	artificial intelligence	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	3 months, 2 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>AI Infrastructure and Operations Fundamentals</u>	artificial intelligence	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	3 weeks, 2 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>AI: an Overview Specialization</u>	artificial intelligence	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	3 weeks, 2 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Calidad de Datos (Data Quality Framework)</u>	data quality	edX	Logyca	Intermediate	4 weeks, 3-5 hours/week	Free	Virtual
<u>PyTorch and Deep Learning for</u>	data quality	edX	Linux Foundation	Intermediate	7 weeks, 1-2 hours/week	Free	Virtual

<u>Decision Makers</u>							
<u>Basics of Data Science</u>	data quality	edX	RWTH Aachen	Intermediate	9 weeks, 5-11 hours/week	Free	Virtual
<u>Total Data Quality Specialization</u>	specialization, data quality	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	1 month, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Introduction to Data Analytics</u>	data quality	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	10 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Measuring Total Data Quality</u>	data quality	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	9 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Healthcare Data Quality and Governance</u>	data quality	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	11 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>ETL and Data Pipelines with Shell, Airflow and Kafka</u>	data quality	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	16 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Information Systems Auditing, Controls and Assurance</u>	auditing, controls	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	3 weeks, 2 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Data-Driven Leadership Skills Specialization</u>	specialization, data quality	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	1 month, 10 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Pre-MBA Quantitative Skills Specialization</u>	specialization, data quality	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	3 months, 4 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual

<u>Design Strategies for Maximizing Total Data Quality</u>	data quality	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	9 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Improving data quality in analytics & ML</u>	data quality	Udemy	-	Intermediate	5.5 hours	€15	Virtual
<u>Data Governance - Complete Course for Beginners</u>	data quality	Udemy	-	Intermediate	3.5 hours	€13	Virtual
<u>Introduction to Hyperledger Self-Sovereign Identity</u>	self sovereign identities	edX	Linux Foundation	Intermediate	3 weeks, 2-3 hours/week	Free	Virtual
<u>Getting Started with Self-Sovereign Identity</u>	self sovereign identities	edX	Linux Foundation	Intermediate	10 weeks, 1-2 hours/week	Free	Virtual
<u>Advanced Blockchain Architectures</u>	self sovereign identities	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	14 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Transacting on the Blockchain</u>	self sovereign identities	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	15 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Blockchain: Foundations and Use Cases</u>	self sovereign identities	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	3 weeks, 3 hours/week	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Blockchain, Cryptoassets, and Decentralized Finance</u>	finance	Coursera	Coursera	Intermediate	17 hours	Course Plus	Virtual
<u>Global Financial</u>	financial markets	Coursera	Rice	Intermediate	20 hours	Course Plus	Virtual

<u>Markets and Instruments</u>							
<u>Identity & Access Management</u>	self sovereign identities	Udemy	-	Intermediate	3 hours	€13	Virtual
<u>Decentralized Identity Systems using Blockchain</u>	self sovereign identities	Udemy	-	Intermediate	1 hour	€13	Virtual